

Supplemental Materials

for the manuscript:

Graph-Based Modeling of Elastic Behavior in Microscale Multi-Phase Concrete using Community-Enhanced GNN

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This document provides extended experimental results, generalization analyses, diagnostic evaluations, and technical details supporting the main manuscript.

S1. Data Pipeline and Microstructure Processing

High-resolution X-ray CT scans (55 μm voxel size) underwent artifact removal, median filtering, and registration. Segmentation thresholds were validated across 50 slices with $\kappa = 0.83$ inter-rater agreement. A perturbation test with $\pm 2\%$ threshold variation and ± 1 voxel jitter confirmed CE-GNN prediction robustness (variation $\leq 3\%$).

Figure S1

Figure S2

Figure S3

Figure S4

Figure S5

Figure S6

Figure S7

Figure S8

S2. Graph Construction Details

Voxel-based RVEs (30^3) are mapped to graphs using Mapper clustering. A multi-lens filter $f(X) = \{\text{variance, entropy, (x,y,z)}\}$ partitions the voxel domain into overlapping subsets. DFS extracts phase-consistent clusters as graph nodes, with edges preserving adjacency and stress-transfer pathways. Node features include phase label, centroid, size, entropy, and topological metrics.

S3. FEM-Based Homogenization

FEM homogenization performed on each RVE used periodic boundary conditions and tetrahedral meshing (refined to $27.5 \mu\text{m}$ at interfaces). Six deformation modes yielded the effective stiffness tensor C_{eff} . Bulk modulus (K) and shear modulus (μ) were computed and used as ground truth for CE-GNN training.

S4. CE-GNN Model Configuration

CE-GNN uses 3 GIN layers (64 units), four-head community-aware attention, betweenness-based graph pruning (top 10%), dropout=0.2, weight decay= $1e-4$, and the Adam optimizer. Unless otherwise stated, the main-manuscript results (including $R^2 \approx 0.97$) were obtained with learning rate = $1e-3$ and batch size = 32.

S5. Sensitivity Analysis

Key hyperparameters, including learning rate, batch size, convolutional depth, and the number of fully connected layers, were varied to assess sensitivity. Within the tested ranges, the best-performing setting in this sweep was learning rate = 0.005 and batch size = 64 with 3 GNN layers and 3 fully connected layers. For clarity and reproducibility, the primary results reported in the main manuscript, including $R^2 \approx 0.97$, use the fixed training configuration stated in Section S4, namely learning rate = $1e-3$ and batch size = 32, unless explicitly noted otherwise. Figures S1–S4

illustrate the R^2 sensitivity across these settings. In addition to training hyperparameters, upstream segmentation can affect derived morphology descriptors and the voxel-to-graph representation; therefore, we recommend assessing robustness by applying plausible segmentation variations and quantifying the induced changes in morphology statistics and the final predictions after reconstructing graphs with the same fixed model configuration.

S6. Generalization Analysis

CE-GNN generalizes well to unseen porosity ranges ($R^2=0.80$), unseen aggregate–matrix ratios (50–60%), and larger RVE sizes (100^3 – 200^3). MAE remains within ~ 1.0 GPa for all cases.

S7. Diagnostic Error Analysis

Residual plots confirm that prediction errors are approximately zero-centered with no visible heteroscedasticity. QQ-plots demonstrate near-normal residual distributions, supporting the stability and unbiased behavior of CE-GNN on the independent test specimens.

S8. Extended Performance Visualizations

Additional performance visualizations compare CNN baselines (DenseNet, EfficientNet, ResNet), the Standard GNN, and CE-GNN. Across bulk modulus, shear modulus, Young’s modulus, Poisson’s ratio, and Lamé parameters, CE-GNN exhibits the tightest error concentration and lowest variance, indicating superior robustness and consistency.

Table S1. Key implementation parameters for the Mapper-based voxel-to-graph transformation (used across all experiments unless otherwise stated).

Item	Parameter (as implemented)	Value used in this study	Where defined	Notes
Mapper cover settings	Cover interval (related to resolution), cover_interval	3 voxels	mapper_DFS.py (CLI arg --cover_interval, default=3)	1D filter along the x-axis; cover windows start at 0, 3, 6, ..., 27 for a 30^3 voxel RVE. Each window spans interval + overlap_pixel voxels (truncated at the boundary).
Mapper overlap & small-component pruning	Overlap ratio, overlap; overlap thickness overlap_pixel = ceil(cover_interval \times overlap); minimum cluster-size threshold threshold = $1e-4 \times N_{\text{vox}}$	overlap = 0.7 \Rightarrow overlap_pixel = 3 voxels; for 30^3 RVEs: threshold = $0.0001 \times 30^3 = 2.7 \approx 3$ voxels	mapper_DFS.py (CLI arg --overlap, default=0.7)	Consecutive cover windows overlap by overlap_pixel voxels; connected components smaller than threshold voxels are discarded (applied per phase). Edges are created from overlaps with overlap_thickness = overlap_pixel.

S9. Experimental Specifications for Specimen Preparation and CT Imaging

CT imaging was performed at 160 kV and 60 μ A. The reconstructed volumes were exported in 16-bit grayscale and then resampled to an isotropic voxel size of 55 μ m prior to phase segmentation, ensuring consistent spatial resolution for voxelization and downstream analysis. Intensity normalization and contrast enhancement were applied before threshold-based phase separation to obtain stable multi-phase labels.